

Chemical Examination of *Crataeva-nurvala*

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THE paper reports the isolation and study of a number of known compounds mainly, sugars, aminoacids, colouring matters, tannins, and a steroidal saponin from the root bark of *Crataeva nurvala*^{1,2}. An unidentified thioglucoside has also been isolated from the same source.

Crataeva-nurvala^{1,2} commonly known as Varuna in Hindi belongs to the N.O. Cappridaceae. It is a small tree with much branched head. It is found almost all over India and Burma in wild or cultivated form. The bark of the plant is stomachic, laxative, antilithic, vesicant, anthelmintic and detergent. In combination with other drugs, it is used in the treatment of snakebite and scorpionsting.

Because of its therapeutic value, the root bark of the plant was selected to investigate it chemically. Other workers^{3,4} have also studied the same plant but none has reported the chemical constituents contained in this paper.

Experimental :

The powdered root-bark of the plant was extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract gave a deposit on cooling which was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and extracted with petroleum ether to remove fatty matters. The residue gave positive tests for saponins, amino-acids, sugars, glycosides, flavonoids and tannins. A small amount of the residue was dissolved in ethanol and chromatographed on paper chromatograms in three different solvent systems. Chromatograms after development^{5,6} showed the presence of lysine-hydrochloride, arginine hydrochloride, cysteic acid, hydroxy-proline, glutamic acid, and α -amino-caprylic acid.

The ethanolic extract also showed the presence of glucose, galactose, and maltose on the paper chromatograms. These were confirmed by co-chromatography with the authentic samples of sugar.

The remaining residue was shaken with water. The water soluble portion was extracted with

ethylacetate. The flavonoids contained in the ethylacetate fraction were separated, and purified over the column of silica gel and on paper chromatograms by eluting the column with different solvents and their mixtures. The flavonoids were identified as rutin and quercetin (aglycone of rutin) by chemical methods and spectral studies. The ethylacetate insoluble portion of water soluble fraction of the residue gave positive tests for saponins. The saponin in this fraction was purified over the silica gel column. The hydrolysis of the saponin with sulphuric acid gave glucose (identified by paper chromatography) in the aqueous hydrolysate. The aglycone from the aqueous hydrolysate was extracted, with chloroform. It was identified as β -sitosterol by its m.p, specific rotation and i.r. spectral studies and confirmed by m.m.p, co-chromatography and completely superimposable i. r. spectrum of the compound with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol. Thus the saponin contains the sapogenin, β -sitosterol and glucose.

The study of the thioglucoside obtained from the methanolic extract of the root-bark is in progress. The study of the nonhydrolysable water insoluble tannin is also in progress.

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